

Intelligent Dermatology: Exploration of Transformer Networks for Skin Disease

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Abstract – The objective of this paper is to explore various existing Transformer networks for diagnostic and classification of complex patterns in dermatological images. Initially designed for natural language processing, transformer networks have shown impressive effectiveness in computer vision tasks, including the detection of skin diseases. In contrast to convolutional neural networks (CNNs) that analyze localized image regions, Transformers process the entire image at once, enabling the capture of both intricate details and broader contextual patterns. This survey reviews how different Transformer models contribute to skin disease classification by enhancing feature extraction, offering better scalability, and achieving improved performance on benchmark datasets such as the International Skin Imaging Collaboration (ISIC), the ISIC Challenge, and HAM10000. The findings emphasize the potential of Transformers to increase diagnostic accuracy, mitigate challenges related to limited data, and support the development of more efficient and interpretable diagnostic systems.

Index Terms - Deep Learning, Skin Disease Classification, Transformer Networks, Explainable AI (XAI), Transfer Learning , Image Classification, Lesion Segmentation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Skin diseases represent some of the most widespread health concerns worldwide, ranging from mild conditions like acne to serious illnesses such as melanoma. While Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have shown high effectiveness in medical imaging tasks, including skin disease classification, their limitations—such as restricted ability to capture global context, high data dependency, and significant computational demands—have prompted the exploration of alternative models. Vision Transformers (ViTs) have emerged as a promising solution, offering potential advantages in addressing these challenges.

In recent years, deep learning models based on Transformers have shown strong abilities in analyzing and classifying skin conditions. Vision Transformers, in particular, have gained traction in skin lesion classification due to their proficiency in capturing both fine-grained and global image features. A range of Transformer-based strategies has been introduced, including lightweight and multimodal models like LiwTERM[1], which fuses lesion images with patient metadata, and SkinSwinViT[2], which employs Swin Transformers for improved attention mechanisms. Other notable innovations include hybrid architectures such as ViTGAN[7], SkinTrans[15], and Medical Vision Transformer (MVT)[14], designed to address challenges like class imbalance and insufficient feature localization. Collectively, these approaches highlight the expanding role of Transformer models in enhancing diagnostic accuracy, improving generalization, and supporting the development of robust and practical automated skin disease diagnosis systems.

The organisation of the paper is as follows: Section 2 presents an overview of the methodology employed in this study, along with a summary of publicly available skin disease datasets. Section 3 delves into a concise analysis of deep learning models, with a particular emphasis on Transformer architectures and their key structural elements. Section 4 discusses the performance evaluation metrics used to assess these models, highlights benchmark results, and addresses the challenges faced in applying these models to real-world clinical scenarios. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with a comprehensive discussion and concluding remarks.

2. METHODOLOGY AND DATASETS

In 2024, several studies investigated novel approaches to classify skin diseases using transformer-based models. Table 1 summarizes the key datasets commonly used for training skin lesion classification models. Several recent studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of Transformer-based approaches in this domain. Luis A. Souza Jr. et al. introduced **LiwTERM**, a lightweight model that integrates Vision Transformers (ViTs) for image analysis and Language Models (LMs) for textual data, showing strong

performance on the **ISIC 2019** dataset [1]. Kun Tang et al. proposed **SkinSwinViT**, which leverages Swin Transformers with both local and global attention mechanisms, achieving improved results on the **ISIC 2018** dataset through data augmentation techniques [2]. In another approach, Rajat Vishwakarma et al. developed a hybrid architecture that combines Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with Transformers to classify **23 types of skin diseases** using the **DermNet** dataset [3].

Karthik et al. introduced a hybrid model that combines Swin Transformers with Dense Group Shuffle Non-Local Attention, which was evaluated on the HAM10000 dataset and showed improved feature representation [6]. Ghanta Sai Krishna et al. proposed a ViT-ViTGAN hybrid model specifically designed to tackle class imbalance issues, achieving high classification accuracy on the HAM10000 dataset [7]. Guang Yang et al. used a ViT-based architecture for skin cancer classification, evaluating both the HAM10000 and Edinburgh DERMOFIT datasets [8]. Additionally, Giansalvo Cirrincione et al. developed a ViT model aimed at distinguishing melanoma from benign lesions, trained on datasets from the ISIC Challenge [4].

Qaisar Abbas et al. proposed a Lightweight Separable Vision Transformer designed to reduce computational complexity while preserving high classification accuracy across multiple datasets, including PH2, ISBI-2017, HAM10000, and ISIC [9]. Sirawich Vachmanus et al. introduced a multimodal model that combines visual features with metadata from the ISIC 2016–2020 and PH2 datasets, resulting in improved diagnostic accuracy [10]. Lin Liu et al. focused on melasma detection, developing a model evaluated on 8,010 facial images captured using the VISIA imaging system [11]. Additionally, Gan Cai et al. introduced a multimodal Transformer architecture that combines image data with metadata, trained on the ISIC 2018 and a proprietary dataset, resulting in enhanced classification performance [12]. Suliman Aladhadh et al. applied the Medical Vision Transformer (MVT) to skin cancer classification, demonstrating its effectiveness on the HAM10000 dataset [13]. Chao Xin et al. developed SkinTrans, a multi-scale Vision Transformer model that enhances classification by capturing both fine-grained details and global contextual information [14]. Collectively, these studies underscore the growing potential of Vision Transformers in advancing the accuracy, generalization, and diagnostic power of automated skin lesion classification systems.

Table 1: Summary of Standard Datasets used in Skin Lesion Classification

S,NO	DATASET	IMAGE SIZE	NO.OF CLASSES
1.	HAM10000[4,5,6,10,14,15]	10,015 × 150,528	7 (AK - Actinic Keratosis, BCC-Basal Cell Carcinoma, BKL – Benign Keratosis-like Lesions, DF – Dermatofibroma, NV – Melanocytic Nevus, MEL – Melanoma, VASC – Vascular Lesions.
2.	ISIC 2019[4]	33,569 × 150,528	8 (MEL – Melanoma,NV – Melanocytic Nevus,BCC – Basal Cell Carcinoma,AKIEC – Actinic Keratosis / Intraepithelial Carcinoma, BKL – Benign Keratosis-like Lesions ,DF – Dermatofibroma,VASC – Vascular Lesions,SCC – Squamous Cell Carcinoma.
3.	ISIC2018 challenge dataset[5,9]	10,015 × 150,528	7(MEL – Melanoma, NV – Melanocytic Nevus, BCC – Basal Cell Carcinoma,AKIEC – Actinic Keratosis / Intraepithelial Carcinoma, BKL – Benign Keratosis-like Lesions (e.g., seborrheic keratoses, solar lentigo), DF – Dermatofibroma VASC – Vascular Lesions (e.g., angiomas, hemorrhage)

3. TRANSFORMERS FOR SKIN LESION CLASSIFICATION

3.1 Transformer Architecture -Vision transformer model

Figure 1 shows how a Vision Transformer (ViT) model works. First, the input image is split into small, equal-sized patches. Each patch is flattened and converted into a vector using a patch embedding layer. These vectors form a sequence of tokens. A special *class token* is added at the beginning of this sequence, which is used later to make the final prediction.

The sequence is then passed through several Transformer Encoder layers. Each of these layers includes attention mechanisms that help the model understand the relationships between different parts of the image. After processing, the output linked to the class token is sent to a classification head, which makes the final decision.

ViT models have shown great results in medical image tasks, like classifying skin diseases. By treating image patches like words in a sentence, ViTs can understand both local details and the bigger picture. This helps them spot important patterns that CNNs might miss. Also, when ViTs are fine-tuned on skin disease datasets after being trained on large general image datasets, they can become very effective and accurate for diagnosis.

Figure 1. Vision Transformer model

The studies in [8], [9], and [11] present innovative Transformer-based methods for classifying skin diseases. In [8], a Vision Transformer (ViT) model is developed with four main components: (1) class rebalancing to handle uneven distribution of skin cancer types, (2) image splitting and tokenization for preparing the input, (3) Transformer encoding to learn important features, and (4) final classification of different skin cancer types. The model uses transfer learning, starting with pretraining on ImageNet and fine-tuning on the HAM10000 dataset.

Study [9] also proposes a ViT-based model focused on distinguishing melanoma from benign lesions, using the ISIC challenge dataset for training and testing. In [11], a different approach uses BEiT (a Vision Transformer pre-trained through masked image modeling) as the image encoder. This model further integrates metadata with visual features, imitating how clinicians consider both image and patient data when making diagnoses. On four public datasets with dermoscopic and smartphone images, the DeepMetaForge model attains a solid average macro F1-score of 87.1%, showcasing the effectiveness of integrating visual and contextual information.

3.2 Transformer Architecture -Hybrid model

The hybrid model for skin disease classification merges the advantages of traditional Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with the advanced attention capabilities of Vision Transformers (ViTs). This approach takes advantage of CNNs' ability to extract local textures and patterns from skin images, while Vision Transformers (ViTs) contribute by capturing global context through self-attention mechanisms. By combining these two architectures, the hybrid model is able to achieve enhanced performance, especially in detecting complex skin lesions that require both detailed local information and broader contextual understanding. This method is particularly effective on large dermatological datasets like ISIC 2019 and HAM10000, where the model benefits from improved generalization and classification accuracy.

Figure 2 . Hybrid Transformer model

As shown in Figure 2, Hybrid Transformer models combine the strengths of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Vision Transformers (ViTs) to boost performance in tasks such as skin disease classification. CNNs are good at capturing local details in images, while Transformers are better at understanding the overall context. By bringing these two approaches together, hybrid models can learn both detailed and broad features from medical images more effectively. LiwTERM [1] introduces a lightweight multimodal Transformer using ViT and tokenizer features in a shallow trainable architecture, offering strong performance with low computational cost. SkinSwinViT [2] combines Swin Transformer and global attention to extract both local and global features, achieving high accuracy on the ISIC2018 dataset. A Convolutional Transformer in [3], enhanced with transfer learning and mix-up augmentation, achieved 73.8% accuracy on the DermNet dataset, supported by further exploration in [4]. The scalable ST model [5] evaluates classification performance under various data splits and augmentation strategies. A dual-track model [6] merges Swin

Transformer with DenseNet-169 and a Group Shuffle Depth-wise block to capture diverse features. ViTGAN [7] tackles class imbalance using GAN-generated images and employs a ViT classifier with explainable AI tools for interpretability. Assist-Dermo [10] proposes a hybrid of ViT and separable convolutions for real-time lesion classification. The MVT model [14] processes image patches through a Transformer pipeline, outperforming traditional models on HAM10000. SkinTrans [15] refines feature representation using ViT's self-attention, achieving over 94% accuracy on both HAM10000 and clinical datasets, highlighting the effectiveness of Transformer architectures in dermatological diagnostics.

4. EVALUATION METHODS AND METRICS

4.1 Evaluation Methods

In 2024, several studies made significant progress in applying Vision Transformer (ViT) models to skin lesion classification. Luis A. Souza Jr. et al. introduced LiwTERM, a lightweight model that combines lesion images with patient metadata, showing strong performance on the PAD UFES-20 and ISIC 2019 datasets [1]. Kun Tang et al. developed SkinSwinViT, which leverages Swin Transformers to improve attention mechanisms, leading to better results on the ISIC 2018 dataset [2]. Rajat Vishwakarma et al. focused on using deep CNNs with the DermNet dataset to diagnose 23 different skin diseases [3]. Also in 2024, Mirco Gallazzi et al. enhanced model generalization by merging multiple datasets for improved multiclass skin lesion classification using transformer-based models [5]. R. Karthik et al. proposed a hybrid architecture that combines Swin Transformers with Dense Group Shuffle Non-Local Attention, achieving strong performance on the HAM10000 dataset, which includes various pigmented skin lesion images [6].

In 2023, several studies highlighted the expanding role of Transformer-based models in skin disease classification and detection. Ghanta Sai Krishna et al. developed a ViT-ViTGAN hybrid model to tackle class imbalance, achieving high accuracy on the HAM10000 dataset [7]. Guang Yang et al. proposed a ViT-based model for skin cancer classification that outperformed traditional models on the Edinburgh DERMOFIT dataset [8]. Giansalvo Cirrincione et al. concentrated on melanoma detection, using the ISIC challenge dataset [4]. Qaisar Abbas et al. introduced a Separable Vision Transformer (SVT), designed to reduce computational complexity while maintaining classification accuracy [9]. Gan Cai et al. enhanced classification performance by integrating ViT with patient metadata [12]. Suliman Aladhadh et al. evaluated the Medical Vision Transformer (MVT) on the HAM10000 dataset [13], and Chao Xin et al. presented SkinTrans, a ViT model focused on improving feature localization for skin cancer detection [14]. These studies collectively illustrate the growing effectiveness and adaptability of Transformer-based models in advancing skin disease diagnosis.

4.2 Performance Evaluation Metrics for Transformer Models

Luis A. Souza Jr. et al. reported balanced accuracy scores of 73% on the ISIC 2019 dataset and 74% on the PAD-UFES-20 dataset for skin lesion classification. Kun Tang et al. and Rajat Vishwakarma et al. evaluated their models using common metrics such as precision, recall (sensitivity), F1-score, and accuracy. Similarly, Mirco Gallazzi et al. and R. Karthik et al. used these standard evaluation metrics to assess their models' performance.

Ghanta Sai Krishna et al. employed Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) along with accuracy to evaluate their hybrid ViT-ViTGAN model. Guang Yang et al. achieved a high classification accuracy of 94.1%, outperforming models like InceptionResNetV2 with soft attention. Giansalvo Cirrincione et al. and Qaisar Abbas et al. used a combination of accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUROC).

Sirawich Vachmanus et al. focused on precision, recall, and F1-score for performance measurement. Lin Liu et al. reported results based on accuracy, sensitivity, and AUC. Gan Cai et al. utilized a comprehensive set of metrics, including accuracy, AUC, sensitivity, specificity, and F1-score. Similarly, Suliman Aladhadh et al. assessed their model using F1-score, specificity, sensitivity, and accuracy, while Chao Xin et al. evaluated accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC.

Table -2 summarizes the performance metrics adopted across the reviewed studies.

METRICS	FORMULAS
Precision	$TP / (TP + FP)$
Recall (Sensitivity):	$TP / (TP + FN)$
Specificity	$TN / (TN + FP)$
Accuracy	$(TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN)$
F1 Score	$2 \times (\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}) / (\text{Precision} + \text{Recall})$
IoU	$TP / (TP + FP + FN)$

Where TP, TN, FP, and FN represent true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives, respectively.

- Accuracy: Measures the proportion of correctly classified instances among all instances.
- Precision: Indicates the proportion of true positive predictions among all positive predictions made by the model.
- Recall (Sensitivity): Reflects the model's ability to identify all actual positive cases.
- Specificity: Represents the proportion of true negative predictions among all actual negative cases.
- F1 Score: The harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balance between the two.

4.3 Comparison of Existing Transformer Models for Skin Disease

Table -3 Key Observations

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Specificity	AUC/AUROC	Remarks
SkinSwinViT	97.88%	97.83%	97.55%	97.79%	99.36%	–	Best all-around performer with consistently high scores
MedViT	98%	–	–	–	–	–	Highest reported accuracy; lacks supporting metrics
Assist-Dermo	95.6%	–	96.7%	–	95%	95%	Strong generalization and diagnostic ability
Hybrid DL + Swin	94.21%	96.62%	96.25%	96.64%	–	–	Excellent balance of performance metrics
Melanoma ViT	94.8%	–	92.8%	–	96.7%	94.8%	High sensitivity and specificity—useful for melanoma detection
Multimodal Transformer	93.81%	–	–	–	–	99%	Highest AUC—best at class distinction even if not top in accuracy

The Table -3 provides a comparative overview of several Vision Transformer (ViT) models currently applied to skin disease diagnosis, highlighting their individual strengths and overall performance. From the comparison of top transformer-based models for skin lesion classification, it is evident that Vision Transformer (ViT) architectures, especially when enhanced with hybrid techniques or multimodal data, can achieve state-of-the-art performance across various clinical metrics.

This systematic review explored various transformer-based methods applied to skin lesion classification and diagnosis. The typical workflow in the studies reviewed included dataset collection, preprocessing, the implementation of transformer models, and performance evaluation using a variety of metrics.

Many of the reviewed studies reported their highest classification accuracy when applying Vision Transformer (ViT) models to skin lesion datasets. These models were frequently benchmarked against state-of-the-art algorithms and traditional Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), with ViTs consistently demonstrating superior performance in terms of accuracy and feature representation.. This suggests that transformer-based models, particularly ViT, generally offer superior performance over conventional CNN approaches in the context of skin lesion analysis. Moreover, nearly 90% of the studies utilized publicly available datasets for their experiments.

Figure 3. Performance Progression of Skin Lesion Classification Models: CNN vs. Hybrid vs. Transformer Architectures

Figure 3 illustrates the average accuracy achieved by three different types of models—CNN, Hybrid, and Transformer—in skin lesion classification tasks. The inference drawn is that transformer-based models not only outperform traditional deep learning approaches in accuracy but also offer flexibility to be optimized for specific clinical goals—whether it's minimizing false negatives (high recall), ensuring reliable classification (high precision), or maintaining diagnostic balance (high F1 Score and AUC). These models are therefore highly promising for integration into automated dermatology diagnostic tools and clinical decision support systems.

4.4 Challenges and Possible Solutions

Deep learning models used for detecting skin diseases face multiple challenges: data is often limited and imbalanced, making accurate training difficult; high intra-class variability means the same disease can look very different across patients; models are often "black boxes," making their decisions hard to interpret; they typically don't express how uncertain they are about a diagnosis; and finally, integrating them into clinics and gaining doctor acceptance proves challenging. Solutions to these issues include using

data augmentation and transfer learning to manage data scarcity, employing ensemble learning to handle varied disease appearances, integrating attention mechanisms and explainable AI for better interpretability, utilizing Bayesian deep learning for uncertainty estimation, and actively involving dermatologists in development and conducting clinical trials to foster adoption.

5.CONCLUSION

In conclusion, transformer-based models, especially Vision Transformers (ViTs), show great promise in overcoming the limitations of traditional CNNs for skin disease classification. These models can capture both local and global features, leading to better accuracy, generalization, and scalability in medical image analysis. Innovations like LiwTERM, SkinSwinViT, ViTGAN, SkinTrans, and Medical Vision Transformer (MVT) address key challenges, such as class imbalance, feature localization, and data scarcity, making them more effective for skin disease diagnosis. Overall, transformer-based models offer great potential for more accurate, accessible, and interpretable skin disease detection in the future.

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